

Measurement of Anion Activity in Electrolytic Solutions with Anion-exchange Resin Membrane Electrodes

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Systematic measurements of the activities of Cl^- , Br^- , I^- , NO_3^- , IO_3^- , and BrO_3^- ions in electrolytic solutions have been made with anion-exchange resin membrane electrodes. The membranes have been prepared using three commercial anionites, Ionac-A-300, Amb. IR-4B, and IRA-400, with polystyrene binder. In most of the cases the range of validity with each of the resin types is from 0.001*m* to 0.1*m* except that the membranes prepared from IRA-400 do not give any satisfactory results with the iodide ions. Membranes are not specific.

The remarkable electrochemical behaviour of ionic membranes, prepared from ion-exchange materials like clays and synthetic resins, has encouraged various workers for their use as electrodes for determination of ionic activities in solutions. Although potentiometric determination of the activities of anions is important in many respects, this method has been applied to a limited number of anionic species because of the lack of suitable electrodes. The clay-membrane electrodes are unsuitable as the exchange reactions on them are entirely cationic. Sollner and Gregor¹ have developed protamine-collecion membranes to measure the activities of chloride, bromide, iodide, and acetate ions. The suitability of anion-exchange resin membranes has also been explored by Sinha² and by Basu³.

For all practical purposes, such standard electrodes as Hg-Hg₂Cl₂ or Ag-AgCl, which are reversible with respect to the chloride ion, are no doubt easily available in suitable forms for the measurement of chloride-ion activity, but require care for their preparation and maintenance. Similarly, bromide or iodide-ion reversible electrodes require careful manipulation to eliminate considerable errors. For nitrate, bromate, or iodate ion, no suitable electrodes are readily available.

Following the successful experiments by Sinha², Basu³ demonstrated the possibility of employing anion-exchange resin membrane electrodes for the measurement of anionic activities like nitrate, etc. The present work is concerned with more systematic measurements of the activities of Cl^- , Br^- , I^- , NO_3^- , IO_3^- , and BrO_3^- ions.

EXPERIMENTAL

The resin membranes were prepared according to Sinha⁴ using three commercial anionites, Ionac-A-300, Amb. IR-4B, and Amb. IR-400 by moulding at 120° and 4000 lbs.

1. *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1954, 58, 409.
2. *This Journal*, 1954, 31, 577.
3. *Science & Culture*, 1956, 21, 447.
4. *This Journal*, 1953, 30, 529.

p.s.i. using polystyrene as binder. The electrodes were prepared by fixing the membranes, cut into small sizes, to one end of a pyrex tubing with 'Durofix' adhesive. The electrodes were then converted into the respective ionic form by thoroughly soaking them for 2 to 3 days in solutions containing a high concentration of the ion concerned. The membranes were checked as usual for absence of asymmetry potential. The membranes showing negligible or zero asymmetry potential were then interposed between solutions of known ion activities. Standard solutions were usually prepared from potassium or sodium salts in such a way as could make the ratio of ion activities of any suitable pair equal to 3:1; the activity coefficients were calculated by graphical method, plotting the known values from Lewis and Randall⁵. The E. M. F. of the following cell:

was measured by means of L & N K₂-type potentiometer in combination with a Hartmann and Braun galvanometer having a sensitivity of 10⁻¹⁰ amps./mm/m. The readings, accurate within ± 0.1 mV, were taken by interchanging the solutions inside and outside the pyrex tubing to check as well as eliminate asymmetry potential, if any.

The equilibrium was attained fairly quickly in concentrated solutions, but in dilute solutions a longer time, often about 24 hours, was required. The reproducibility of the measurements was checked by repeated changes of solutions. The electrical resistance of the membranes was found to be within one megohm. For comparison, the theoretical E. M. F.'s. were calculated by means of the simple Nernst equation:

$$E = \frac{RT}{nF} \ln \frac{a_2}{a_1}$$

which has been proved to hold good in the case of such membrane electrodes as those used here. The results are recorded in Tables I to III. In these experiments either the potassium or sodium salts were only used.

TABLE I

Nitrate-ion activity.

Activities (inside/outside).	Mean observed Ionac-A-300.	E. M. F. with membranes of		Theoretical E.M.F.
		IR-4B.	IRA-400.	
0.00291/0.00097	28.6 mV	28.5 mV	27.8 mV	28.1 mV
0.00873/0.00291	27.8	28.0	28.1	28.1
0.02619/0.00873	27.0	27.5	27.8	28.1
0.07857/0.02619	26.0	26.5	26.9	28.1

5, "Thermodynamics and Free Energy of Chemical Substances",

TABLE III

Activities (Inside/outside)	Mean observed E. M. F. using membranes of						Theoretical E.M.F.
	Ionac-A-300. IR-4B. IRA-400.			Ionac-A-300 IR-4B IBA-400			
	A. Bromate ion activity.						
0.00285/0.00095	28.0 mV	27.0 mV	27.6 mV	27.3 mV	27.0 mV	27.9 mV	28.1 mV
0.00855/0.00285	28.5	27.0	27.8	27.0	26.5	27.0	28.1
0.02565/0.00855	27.0	26.5	26.0	26.0	25.8	26.3	28.1
0.07695/0.02565	25.0	25.3	26.0	24.0	24.5	25.8	28.1

*Same for Bromate ion.

DISCUSSION

The results recorded above have been graphically represented in Figs. 1 and 2. From the data and the graphs, it can be seen that in most cases the experimental E. M. F. values are slightly lower. This lowering, more prominent at higher concentrations, may be caused by the leakage of the 'non-critical' ion. A similar lowering was also observed by Sollner and his co-workers¹ in their studies with protamine-collodion membranes. They found the best agreement between the calculated and experimental values for chloride ion when used as magnesium chloride. If the predominantly basic resins contain any weak acidic groups (e. g. phenolic groups), these are likely to set up a small opposing E. M. F. in presence of the sodium or potassium ions.

FIG. 1. E.M.F. /log $1/a$ curve for NO_3^- ion with $a_1 : a_2 = 3$.

FIG. 2. E.M.F. /log $1/a$ curve for Br^- ion and I^- ion with $a_1 : a_2 = 3$.

In the dilute ranges, where the results are more in accord with the theoretical values, the resin electrodes perform quite satisfactorily. In most of the cases, the range of validity with each of the resin types is from 0.001 molal to 0.1 molal except that the membranes prepared from IRA-400 do not give any satisfactory results with the iodide ions. These membranes were found to develop a reddish colour on their surface after a long contact with the iodide ions. Since the chemistry of the resin itself is not known with certainty, the abnormal behaviour of the membranes of this resin towards the iodide ion could not be explained.

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